

PYTHON AND ITS LIBRARIES. PROCESSING DIGITAL INFORMATION USING MATPLOTLIB AND JUPYTER FEATURES.

*Shokhrukh Ibodullayevich Cholliyev¹, Malika Zoyir qizi Ergasheva²,
Maftunakhon Zhurabekovna Safarova³.*

¹ assistant, TUIT named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi

² master, TUIT named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi

³ assistant, TUIT named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi

maftunasafarova94@mail.ru

Annotation: The Python programming language has changed so much in recent years that it has covered many areas. For example, Python is considered one of the most reliable programming languages in the fields of Data Science, Deep learning, Machine learning, AI and web programming. When working with data in artificial intelligence, neural networks, and in the above areas, visualization of problem solutions helps to visualize the accuracy of the solution. The Matplotlib library helps us to create a visual image. In this dissertation, we will focus on how to process an image, how massive it is, and how to change the contrast in image processing.

Keywords: python, matplotlib, opencvpython, jupyter, numpy, pandas, pytorch, array, pseudocolor schemas.

Аннотация: За последние годы язык программирования Python настолько изменился, что охватил множество областей. Например, Python считается одним из самых надежных языков программирования в областях науки о данных, глубокого обучения, машинного обучения, искусственного интеллекта и веб-программирования. При работе с данными в искусственном интеллекте, нейронных сетях и в вышеперечисленных областях визуализация решения проблем помогает визуализировать точность решения. Библиотека Matplotlib помогает нам создать визуальный образ. В этой диссертации мы сосредоточимся на том, как обрабатывать изображение, насколько оно массивно и как изменить контраст при обработке изображения.

Ключевые слова: python, matplotlib, opencvpython, jupyter, numpy, pandas, pytorch, массив, схемы псевдоцветов.

The 21st century is the century of information and communication technologies, we cannot imagine our life without technology, the urgency of the problem lies in the fact that there used to be black and white photographs, films without color images, and now, thanks to programming technologies, the conversion of black and white films and images into the color format just got a lot easier. Below we will focus on how to process not only black and white images, but also color images, how to change its array appearance, appearance and image contrast.

**Installing Python and its libraries
(matplotlib, jupyter);**

Import image data into a Numpy array;

**Drawing Numpy arrays as images and
Pseudocolor schemes;**

Now let's put the above sequence of actions into practice.

**1. Installing Python and its libraries
(matplotlib, jupyter):**

First, we download the required Python version from <https://www.python.org/>.

Let's write the name of Python Packageni and find out how to install it. Then download pip3 install matplotlib and install it in a cmd window.

There are several IDLEs available to work with Python, python IDLE, Pycharm, Spyder, Jupyter, and many more environments.

The most convenient way to work with Matplotlib is with Jupyter. Install Jupyter. After we have installed Jupiter, type Jupiter notebook in the cmd window and press Enter, then the following Jupiter working window will appear in our browser. (Picture 1)

Picture 1

Then select *python3* from the *new* section, and we will have a window for writing code (Picture 1).

We import libraries to create the software we need.

Picture 2

2. Import image data into a Numpy array:

```
img = mpimg.imread('C:\\Users\\User\\Desktop\\Qor leopardi.png')
print(img)

[[ [0.09411765 0.09411765 0.09411765]
  [0.12156863 0.12156863 0.12156863]
  [0.10588235 0.10588235 0.10588235]
  ...
  [0.24313726 0.24313726 0.24313726]
  [0.23529412 0.23529412 0.23529412]
  [0.21568628 0.21568628 0.21568628] ]

[[ [0.13333334 0.13333334 0.13333334]
  [0.14509805 0.14509805 0.14509805]
  [0.08627451 0.08627451 0.08627451]
  ...
  [0.22352941 0.22352941 0.22352941]
  [0.21568628 0.21568628 0.21568628]
  [0.21568628 0.21568628 0.21568628] ]
```

Picture 3

As mentioned above, each image is composed of an array of numbers. Pay attention to this type - numbers between number and float 32 (0 and 1). Matplotlib converted 8 bits of data from each channel to floating point data from 0.0 to 1.0.

Since the image is black and white, R, G and B are similar to each other.

3. Drawing Numpy arrays as images and Pseudocolor schemes:

So your data is in an undefined array (imported or generated). In **Matplotlib**, this is

done with the `imshow()` function. This gives us the ability to display the image and an easy way to manipulate it (Picture 4).

Picture 4.

You can also create any *numpy* array. Now let's talk about using *Pseudocolor* schematics in drawings. *Pseudocolor* can be a useful tool for increasing contrast and making data easier to visualize. This is especially useful when presenting data with projectors - their contrast is usually low. *Pseudocolor* only applies to low luminance single channel grayscale images, our image can be processed as follows using the following special codes. (Picture 5)

Picture 5

Note that you can change color maps in existing objects using the `set_cmap()` method. You can use `colorbar()` to see the range of colors.

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